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Artificial compressibility for smoothed particle hydrodynamics using pressure smoothing

Joe J. De Courcy¹, Thomas C.S. Rendall^{1,*}, Brano Titurus¹, Lucian Constantin^{1,2} and Jonathan E. Cooper¹

¹Department of Aerospace Engineering, University of Bristol, U.K.

²SATAS Centre of Excellence, Military Technical Academy “Ferdinand I”, Bucharest, Romania

*thomas.rendall@bristol.ac.uk

Abstract—The advantages of using artificial compressibility in SPH are explored using a number of test cases, including a hydrostatic column, dam-break and violent sloshing. These benefits include pressure field smoothness by eliminating false acoustic waves and improved quality of results for fluid-structure interaction problems. Theoretical links are also drawn between pressure/velocity correction incompressible SPH and artificial compressibility, in addition to a further important link to the δ -SPH method. These comparisons suggest that artificial compressibility sits within a common framework with ISPH and δ -SPH.

I. INTRODUCTION

Many applications of SPH involve incompressible flows (potentially coupled to a compressible air phase), although early usage of SPH in this area made use of compressible methods adapted to work for incompressible problems, most clearly through weakly compressible SPH (WCSPH) [1]. WCSPH solves mass and momentum conservation together with an artificial equation of state to link to pressure, but introduces stiffness in this form and together with the variable particle positions inherent to SPH can lead to noise in pressure fields. Strictly incompressible SPH (ISPH) [2] applies the pressure correction methods of incompressible mesh-based methods to SPH, solving a pressure Poisson equation, and leads to improvements in the quality of the derived pressure fields where significantly lower levels of noise exist, especially when particle shifting is also used [3] to maintain advantageous particle distributions. Like all pressure or velocity correction methods ISPH comes at the cost of a discrete Poisson solve; this overhead can be considerable, although the method has been notably scaled [4]. The desire for a method providing good quality (in terms of noise) pressure fields but avoiding the linear solve cost partly motivated developments that led to δ -SPH [5], which applies smoothing terms within the mass conservation equation, and taken together with appropriate shifting, provides good particle distributions and noise-free pressure fields. In comparison, the artificial compressibility SPH (ACSPH) approach applied here marches a differential equation for pressure, usually based on velocity divergence, until convergence to an incompressible field is reached.

Two objectives drive the developments in this work. Although at a much lower level than for the original WCSPH form, residual compressible behaviour is an artefact that can hamper δ -SPH for violent flows and for those involving

fluid-structure interaction. This behaviour leads to pressure waves that introduce temporal noise, sharp spatial gradients and variations in coupled dynamic fluid-structure response. Furthermore, viewing WCSPH, ISPH and δ -SPH methods as separate methods is not helpful, and misses opportunities to rationalise understanding and open routes to further potentially valuable techniques.

The first goal of this work is to develop a fully incompressible implementation of SPH based on artificial compressibility (ACSPH) that avoids the costs associated with ISPH, and which preserves the smooth pressure field properties of δ -SPH, while eliminating undesired compressible behaviour. The second goal is to draw clear links between the underlying theory of ISPH, δ -SPH and ACSPH in order to expose potential for future improvement of each of those methods.

II. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

Adaptation of compressible mesh-based schemes for incompressible problems has followed one of three paths. The first and most general in terms of physics has been to apply preconditioning [6], and this is the approach used for problems that are neither fully incompressible nor fully compressible. The second and third paths to modelling full incompressibility are artificial compressibility [7] and the extensively developed correction approaches [8], [9] (typically pressure-Poisson equation (PPE) type). As will be shown later, these are decidedly similar.

A. Artificial compressibility

The focus in this work will be on fully incompressible flow, where the velocity field is solenoidal and governed by Newton’s 2nd law as

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v} = 0, \quad \frac{D\mathbf{v}}{Dt} = -\frac{\nabla p}{\rho} + \nu \nabla^2 \mathbf{v} + \mathbf{f} \quad (1)$$

Artificial compressibility will be explored in this work. As originally introduced by Chorin [7] this links the rate of change of pressure in a pseudo time variable τ to the divergence of velocity

$$\frac{Dp}{D\tau} = -k_1 \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v} \quad (2)$$

such that once $\frac{Dp}{D\tau} = 0$ then $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v} = 0$ is satisfied. Notation for material derivatives is adopted here for clarity rather than function, as these differentials will later be integrated on SPH

particles that update positions during iteration, and velocities in pseudo time ultimately vanish on loop convergence. Originally this approach was used to time march to the solution of a steady problem [7], but it may also be used in pseudo time to march sequential timesteps of time accurate unsteady problems to convergence, as will be performed here. The use of pseudo time permits exact incompressibility, but it is also possible to integrate the pressure in time directly without subiteration, although in this case the scaling on divergence needs to be correctly chosen to ensure time accuracy [10].

These approaches work well with meshes, but SPH shows significant noise because the particles themselves, which constitute the mesh, move at each timestep. In turn this renders the pressure field susceptible to noise. Intuitively the choice of the continuity/mass residual to drive pressure is effective, but it is not the only valid or useful alternative. The pressure field must of course satisfy conservation of mass, but it must also satisfy the momentum equation, which is often achieved by solving the discrete equations sequentially at each step. However, this is a relatively mild approach to enforce this condition, and not sufficient for avoiding noise in SPH. A clear alternative is to drive the pressure evolution in pseudo time using the divergence of the momentum equation *in addition* to the mass residual. This introduces a Laplacian pressure term, which although largely unnecessary for Eulerian methods (likely due to mesh smoothing effects) is extremely useful in an SPH method. The inclusion of the momentum divergence in the pressure residual forces the pressure equation to evolve towards a spatially smooth solution, with a scaling as

$$\frac{Dp}{D\tau} = -k_1 \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v} + k_2 \nabla \cdot \left(\frac{D\mathbf{v}}{Dt} + \frac{\nabla p}{\rho} - \nu \nabla^2 \mathbf{v} \right) \quad (3)$$

This result may also be derived from conservation of energy in the real fluid system, when including heat diffusion, as described by Dupuy *et al.* [10], or also via entropy arguments as by Clausen [11]. Summarising from Dupuy *et al.* [10]

$$\frac{Dp}{Dt} = -\gamma p \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v} + (\gamma - 1) \nabla \cdot k \nabla T \quad (4)$$

where providing $\rho e = \frac{p}{\gamma - 1}$ and the Prandtl number $P_r = \frac{c_p \mu}{k}$ then the temperature term may be written in terms of pressure to give

$$\frac{Dp}{Dt} = -\gamma p \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v} + \frac{\gamma \nu}{P_r} \nabla \cdot \nabla p \quad (5)$$

and the divergence term is then scaled for suitable behaviour and is consistent with the original artificial compressibility approach of Chorin [8].

The entropy arguments made by Clausen as part of ‘entropically damped artificial compressibility’ (EDAC) have found application within SPH [12], [13], and entropy arguments are equivalent to those based around the energy equation in this case. Indeed, the momentum equation is also a suitable route to derive those Laplacian contributions, as used above. The rate of divergence term may also then be considered as a damping term which vanishes fully on convergence of the pseudo time

loop, and its contribution may be scaled separately (here for ρ as a constant). Also, there is no restriction against including an arbitrary derivative of pressure of order n using a similar argument to give

$$\frac{Dp}{D\tau} = -k_1 \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v} + k_2 \frac{\nabla \cdot \nabla p}{\rho} + k_3 \frac{D(\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v})}{D\tau} + k_n \nabla^n p \quad (6)$$

The use of higher derivatives is important for this work in the context of the compressible Jameson-Schmidt-Turkel (JST) [14] scheme, which stabilises the Euler system effectively and captures shocks well for compressible problems. The JST approach uses a combination of 2nd and 4th differences, whereby these differences are applied to each of the differential equations for mass, momentum and energy. A pressure switch activates in order to switch the system from 4th (in smooth areas) to 2nd (in non-smooth areas) when a shock is detected. Use of 2nd differences would stabilise the system reliably, but is too dissipative in general and would lead to diffuse shocks and spurious numerical drag in aerodynamics, motivating the use of 4th differences instead for smooth regions of the flow.

B. Prediction/correction methods

Returning to ACSPH, it is instructive to note that this system may also be solved retaining only the parts originating from the momentum equation (in which case the rate of divergence must be with respect to real time), giving

$$\frac{\nabla \cdot \nabla p}{\rho} = -\frac{D(\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v})}{Dt} - \nu \nabla \cdot \nabla^2 \mathbf{v} = -\frac{D(\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v})}{Dt} - \nu \nabla^2 \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v} \quad (7)$$

From this result stems the families of incompressible methods, including the standard, incremental and rotational incremental pressure/velocity forms (in the terminology of Guermond [15], which should be consulted for a detailed treatment). For simplicity the (inviscid) incremental form shall be discussed here, but the arguments hold broadly.

$$\frac{D\tilde{\mathbf{v}}^{i+1}}{Dt} = -\frac{\nabla p^i}{\rho}, \quad \frac{D\mathbf{v}^{i+1}}{Dt} = -\frac{\nabla p^{i+1}}{\rho}, \quad \frac{D\mathbf{v}^i}{Dt} = -\frac{\nabla p^{i+1}}{\rho} \quad (8)$$

The left result here is integrated to find the intermediate velocity $\tilde{\mathbf{v}}^{i+1}$, which importantly uses p^i , or, a higher order extrapolation that estimates p^{i+1} , and this is termed ‘pressure correction’ because the pressure correction comes after the velocity prediction. Ideally, p^{i+1} itself would be used, as in the middle result, but as this is the objective of the calculation it is not yet available. The ‘velocity correction’ approach corresponds to the right hand result where the velocity correction will be the final step. In the inviscid case, these differences are simply reduced to either starting with pressure or velocity for the step, so for brevity of argument, no further distinction is drawn.

The ‘incremental’ equation is constructed with appropriate subtraction as

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{D(\mathbf{v}^{i+1} - \tilde{\mathbf{v}}^{i+1})}{Dt} &= - \frac{\nabla(p^{i+1} - p^i)}{\rho} \\ \nabla \cdot \frac{D(\mathbf{v}^{i+1} - \tilde{\mathbf{v}}^{i+1})}{Dt} &= - \frac{\nabla^2(p^{i+1} - p^i)}{\rho} \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

with $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}^{i+1} = 0$ then

$$\nabla \cdot \frac{D(\tilde{\mathbf{v}}^{i+1})}{Dt} = \frac{\nabla^2(p^{i+1} - p^i)}{\rho} \quad (10)$$

This is the result commonly used to solve for the pressure field in many pressure correction approaches, including most implementations of ISPH. The approach of Timmermans *et al.* [16] has also been explored for ISPH [17]; this has the effect of adjusting the scaling on rate of divergence depending on the order of backward differentiation formula (BDF) that is chosen. However, the BDF stencils cannot remove the error associated with the initial estimated pressure used to find $\tilde{\mathbf{v}}^{i+1}$. This error can only be reduced by improving the pressure extrapolation accuracy at that step, or perhaps preferably, looping the process so that the output of the Poisson solve is reused to iteratively find an improved $\tilde{\mathbf{v}}^{i+1}$. This also forces the ‘pressure correction’ and ‘velocity correction’ techniques to become identical (assuming convergence within the loops), with the only difference being if the loop starts with pressure or velocity. This also makes arguments about whether for example \mathbf{v} or $\tilde{\mathbf{v}}$ is the true velocity immaterial, as they would be forced to the same value.

This approach will cause the time accuracy to be dependent on the BDF (or other) stencil, and will also force $\tilde{\mathbf{v}}^{i+1} \Rightarrow \mathbf{v}^{i+1}$ if the loop converges. In general it appears this is not done due to the cost of repeated Poisson solves and the sufficiency of using higher order extrapolations, but for comparative purposes here the approach could be written (non-incrementally, since the loop would run to convergence) with iteration counter k as

$$-\nabla \cdot \frac{D(\mathbf{v}^{i+1,k})}{Dt} = \frac{\nabla^2 p^{i+1,k+1}}{\rho} \quad (11)$$

which makes it clearer that these approaches can be thought of as iterations around the divergence of the momentum equation, although in practice a single step is used. The study of this iterative approach by Aoussou *et al.* [18] is especially notable.

To cast this as the pseudo time artificial compressibility result then only requires reintroduction of the divergence and rate terms (counter k omitted as it would reappear after discretising the rate term, and including the same scalings as before)

$$\frac{Dp}{D\tau} - k_3 \nabla \cdot \frac{D(\mathbf{v}^{i+1})}{Dt} = -k_1 \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v} + k_2 \frac{\nabla^2 p^{i+1}}{\rho} \quad (12)$$

It is therefore clear that pressure correction approaches (and thus also velocity correction approaches) and artificial compressibility, independent of the numerical formulation used, are close siblings, merely differing in the type of solve used

for the pressure equation. This of course maps through to ISPH and ACS-SPH; where ISPH uses a full (usually iterative) linear solve for pressure on the pressure Poisson equation (PPE), ACS-SPH iterates this alongside divergence to drive a differential system instead. This route to the PPE can also be used to formulate a pressure equation for compressible flows, or to improve error reduction between timesteps for incompressible ones.

C. Similarity to δ -SPH

A further question remains in ascertaining any similarity to the δ -SPH method. The continuity equation with δ -SPH correction [5] is

$$\frac{D\rho_i}{Dt} = \rho_i \sum_j \mathbf{v}_{ij} \cdot \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j + \delta h c_0 \mathcal{D}_i \quad (13)$$

where δ is a constant set at 0.1, and c_0 is the speed of sound of the fluid. \mathcal{D}_i is calculated using

$$\mathcal{D}_i = 2 \sum_j \psi_{ji} \frac{\mathbf{x}_{ji} \cdot \nabla W_{ij}}{|\mathbf{x}_{ji}|^2} V_j \quad (14)$$

$$\psi_{ji} = (\rho_j - \rho_i) - \frac{1}{2} \left(\langle \nabla \rho \rangle_i^L + \langle \nabla \rho \rangle_j^L \right) \cdot \mathbf{x}_{ji} \quad (15)$$

The first term $(\rho_i - \rho_j)$ on the right hand side of equation (15) leads to an approximation of $\nabla \cdot \nabla \rho$ when substituted in the summation of equation (14). This immediately implies that δ -SPH applies a term broadly equivalent to a Laplacian pressure smoothing, but in a weakly compressible context, implemented via density. The continuous equation being solved is of the type $\frac{D\rho}{Dt} = k_{1\delta} \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v} + k_{2\delta} \nabla \cdot \nabla \rho + \dots$

To draw a closer parallel, the equations of state for WCS-SPH fall in to the linear and nonlinear categories broadly as

$$p = c^2 (\rho - \rho_0) \quad \text{and} \quad p = \frac{\rho_0 c^2}{\gamma} \left(\left(\frac{\rho}{\rho_0} \right)^\gamma - 1 \right) \quad (16)$$

Rewriting an equation for pressure using the WCS-SPH equations of state gives

$$\frac{Dp}{Dt} = c^2 \frac{D\rho}{Dt} = -c^2 \rho \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v} = -c^2 \rho_0 \frac{\rho}{\rho_0} \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v} \quad (17)$$

or

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{Dp}{Dt} &= \frac{c^2 \rho_0 \gamma}{\gamma \rho_0} \left(\frac{\rho}{\rho_0} \right)^{\gamma-1} \frac{D\rho}{Dt} \\ &= -c^2 \left(\frac{\rho}{\rho_0} \right)^{\gamma-1} \rho \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v} = -c^2 \rho_0 \left(\frac{\rho}{\rho_0} \right)^\gamma \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v} \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

which makes the comparison to the k_1 term of artificial compressibility clear. Depending on the equation of state used, k_1 is proportional to the density ratio or a power of it.

The suggestion here is that δ -SPH is similar to artificial compressibility, albeit with iterations in real time rather than pseudo time. In detail, they are not identical due to δ -SPH having quite specific scalings on the second derivative term. Applying δ -SPH using a high speed of sound means the density fluctuations remain small and usually propagate

faster than relevant flow velocities, and is nearly equivalent to running ACSPH with one iteration per time step. In terms of software, it is clear any weakly compressible δ -SPH code may be transformed to ACSPH by removing the equation of state, specifying the artificial compressibility parameter k_1 and adding a pseudo time loop within the existing time loop.

III. ACSPH DISCRETISATION

Within ACSPH particles are integrated in pseudo time (τ) rather than real time, such that they do not directly move with the Lagrangian velocity (\mathbf{v}) during subiterations. Considering this in the velocity equation (also including a pseudo time derivative), the velocity of particle motion within pseudo time $\tilde{\mathbf{v}}$ (note this is separate to the notation used earlier) is therefore defined as

$$\frac{D\mathbf{x}}{D\tau} + \frac{D\mathbf{x}}{Dt} = \mathbf{v} + \delta\mathbf{v} \Rightarrow \tilde{\mathbf{v}} := \frac{D\mathbf{x}}{D\tau} = \mathbf{v} + \delta\mathbf{v} - \frac{D\mathbf{x}}{Dt} \quad (19)$$

where an arbitrary perturbation velocity $\delta\mathbf{v}$ is included with the intent of introducing a particle shifting scheme consistently in the equations of motion. On convergence of the dual time scheme $\tilde{\mathbf{v}} \rightarrow \mathbf{0}$ and the standard Lagrangian behaviour is recovered, $\frac{D\mathbf{x}}{Dt} = \mathbf{v} + \delta\mathbf{v}$. Knowing that integration is performed using a modified advection velocity the material derivative must be defined to respect this

$$\frac{D(\bullet)}{D\tau} = \frac{\partial(\bullet)}{\partial\tau} + \tilde{\mathbf{v}} \cdot \nabla(\bullet) \quad (20)$$

Applying this to the pressure/continuity equation and using standard SPH gradient operators the continuity is discretised as

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{Dp_i}{D\tau} = & -k_1\rho_0 \sum_j (\mathbf{v}_j - \mathbf{v}_i) \cdot \nabla W_{ij} V_j + k_2 h D_i^p \\ & - p_i \sum_j (\tilde{\mathbf{v}}_j - \tilde{\mathbf{v}}_i) \cdot \nabla W_{ij} V_j \\ & + \sum_j (p_j \tilde{\mathbf{v}}_j - p_i \tilde{\mathbf{v}}_i) \cdot \nabla W_{ij} V_j \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

Equations 17 and 18 show how the k_1 parameter can be defined, but it was found these can result in an overly stiff numerical system and subsequent instability. However, as time accuracy is not required in the pseudo time iterations the choice of k_1 is essentially free, and driven by the requirement for good convergence and robustness. Therefore, the parameter β is introduced as

$$\beta = \frac{CFL_{ps} h}{\Delta\tau}, \quad k_1 = \beta^2, \quad k_2 = 0.1\beta \quad (22)$$

which is essentially the effective pseudo time wave speed controlled by a CFL condition, where CFL_{ps} can be set according to the standard values for WCSPH time-integration schemes. Following from equation (21) D^p is a spatial derivative of pressure representing a smoothing term, weighted by $0.1h\beta$, which is equivalent to $0.1hc_0$ used within the δ -SPH scheme considering $c_0 \approx \beta$. Two discretisations for D^p are explored within this work, one a pressure Laplacian with free-surface

corrections and the other a JST style scheme (subsequently denoted as AC-2L and AC-JST). First, the pressure Laplacian is defined as

$$\begin{aligned} D_i^{\Delta L} &= \sum_j 2\psi_{ij}^p \frac{\mathbf{x}_{ij}}{\|\mathbf{x}_{ij}\|^2} \cdot \nabla W_{ij} V_j \\ \psi_{ij}^p &= (p_i - p_j) - \frac{1}{2} (\langle \nabla p \rangle_i^L + \langle \nabla p \rangle_j^L) \cdot \mathbf{x}_{ij} \\ \langle \nabla p \rangle_i^L &= \sum_j (p_j - p_i) \mathbf{L}_i \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

Where unsurprisingly, this takes the form of the standard δ -SPH diffusion term cast in terms of pressure. The Jameson-Schmidt-Turkel style scheme is composed of a blend between fourth and second order pressure terms defined as,

$$D_i^{JST} = \epsilon_2 D_i^{\Delta L} + \epsilon_4 D_i^{\Delta^2} \quad (24)$$

where $D_i^{\Delta^2}$ the bi-harmonic pressure operator evaluated through nesting the Brookshaw pressure Laplacians [19], i.e. nesting (23 without the renormalized pressure gradients included ($\langle \nabla p \rangle$)), this is to ensure the JST scheme can be evaluated in two particle-particle loops and has the same cost as (23). The weighting coefficients are defined as $\epsilon_2 = \kappa_2 \min(1, \phi)$ and $\epsilon_4 = \min(0, \kappa_4 - \epsilon_2)$ where the switch is based on a metric of the pressure gradient

$$\phi_i = \left[\sum_j \left| \frac{p_i - p_j}{p_i + p_j} \right| W_{ij} V_j \right] / \sum_j W_{ij} V_j \quad (25)$$

However, not including the renormalized gradients in ψ_{ij} can cause free surface diffusion, hence $D_i^{\Delta L}$ is always activated at the surface in this scheme by setting $\phi_i = 1$ for particles within a kernel support radius of the surface. κ_2 and κ_4 are set to 1/2 and 1/32, respectively. Continuing, momentum is discretised as

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{D\mathbf{v}_i}{D\tau} + \frac{D\mathbf{v}_i}{Dt} = & -\frac{1}{\rho_0} \sum_j (p_i + p_j) \nabla W_{ij} V_j \\ & + \nu \rho_0 K \sum_j \frac{\mathbf{v}_{ij} \cdot \mathbf{x}_{ij}}{\|\mathbf{x}_{ij}\|^2} \nabla W_{ij} V_j + \mathbf{f}_i \\ & + \sum_j (\tilde{\mathbf{v}}_j \otimes \mathbf{v}_j + \tilde{\mathbf{v}}_i \otimes \mathbf{v}_i) \nabla W_{ij} V_j \\ & - \mathbf{v}_i \sum_j (\tilde{\mathbf{v}}_j - \tilde{\mathbf{v}}_i) \nabla W_{ij} V_j \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

Noting that on convergence of the pseudo time iterations $\tilde{\mathbf{v}} \rightarrow \mathbf{0}$ and $\frac{d}{d\tau} \rightarrow 0$, resulting in the standard SPH formulation. Here \mathbf{f} is the particle body force, including gravitational, structural accelerations (when the non-inertial reference frame is used within FSI computations) and the CCSF surface tension term of Vergnaud *et al.* [20].

Unsteady simulation of ACSPH is performed used dual-time integration, taking the form

$$\mathbf{u} = \begin{Bmatrix} p \\ \mathbf{x} \\ \mathbf{v} \end{Bmatrix}, \quad \frac{D\mathbf{u}}{D\tau} = \mathbf{r}^* = \mathbf{r} - \mathbf{I}_c \frac{D\mathbf{u}}{Dt} \quad (27)$$

where \mathbf{r} is a vector of the discrete continuity, velocity and momentum equations as computed from equations (21), (19) and (26). \mathbf{I}_c is a cancellation matrix with diagonal $\{0, 1, 1\}$ to ensure a divergence-free solution. A second-order accurate backward differentiation formula is used to evaluate the real-time derivatives and a three-stage Runge-Kutta scheme used to march the pseudo time iterations to convergence ($\mathbf{r}^* = \mathbf{0}$).

Finally, no special boundary treatment is required in AC-SPH, for the solid or surface conditions and standard WCSPH approaches can be employed. Therefore, the ghost-particle boundary conditions of Adami *et al.* [21] are used along with the free-surface detection of Marrone *et al.* [22]. The particle shifting procedure of Michel *et al.* [23] is used to evaluate $\delta\mathbf{v}$ within (19). To provide comparison against WCSPH the δ -ALE-SPH method of Sun *et al.* [24] (equivalent to the constant mass scheme of Anutono *et al.* [25]) is used. To ensure dissipative properties are consistent between the AC and δ -SPH results shown, the standard artificial viscosity is imposed, $\nu = \alpha_\nu h c_0 / K$ with α_ν set to 0.01 for all cases. Further the Wendland C2 kernel is used with $h/\Delta x = 2$.

IV. RESULTS

In the following section a series of test cases are presented to assess ACSPH, focusing on the improvements in pressure prediction and the resulting quality of fluid-structure interaction cases. The first two cases are standard SPH benchmarks and the final case is a difficult FSI problem characterised by repeated fluid impacts.

A. Hydrostatic water column supported by an elastic plate

This case considers a column of water initially in hydrostatic equilibrium and with an elastic bottom plate. At the start of the simulation the hydrodynamic pressure loads the plate, causing high frequency oscillations to occur within the stiff plate (where the first structural mode oscillates at 254 Hz), which are subsequently dissipated. Generally this case is used to test the robustness and accuracy of fluid-structure coupled solvers, however, here it is used to illustrate the difference between incompressible and weakly compressible fluid models in an FSI setting. The physical parameters of this test case follow directly from Fourey *et al.* [26]. Here the resolution is set to $H/\Delta x = 500$.

Structural motion is found from time-integration of the normal mode shapes computed from FE, resulting in a partitioned, strongly coupled FSI solution. The elastic plate was decomposed into 10 orthogonal shapes, resulting in the matrix of mode shapes \mathbf{E} (the linear transform from FE node Cartesian displacements $\Delta\mathbf{u}_s$ to the participation factors of each shape \mathbf{q}) and the frequency of the modes ω . Considering a standard mass-damping-stiffness equation cast in modal coordinates, the structural equation of motion is

$$\ddot{\mathbf{q}} + [2\omega\zeta]\dot{\mathbf{q}} + [\omega^2]\mathbf{q} = \mathbf{f}_m, \quad \Delta\mathbf{u}_s = \mathbf{E}\mathbf{q}, \quad \mathbf{f}_m = \mathbf{E}^T \mathbf{f}_s \quad (28)$$

which is integrated in time using the implicit Newmark-beta method with the constant average acceleration approach to

ensure unconditional numerical stability. As the SPH and FE grids are non-conforming, a radial basis function interpolation was built to transfer force and kinematics between the two solvers. Finally, a small structural damping was applied with ζ set to 0.01 on each considered mode, to differentiate between fluid and structural induced effects.

Fig. 1: Snapshots of the hydrostatic water column with elastic bottom, left figure shows instant following the first acoustic wave impact with the plate.

Figure 2(a) shows the displacement of the plate midpoint for the two ACSPH and δ -SPH schemes, where the insets show the initial and final regions of the time series. Following simulation start and loading of the plate, a high-frequency oscillation of the plate is observed at the first bending frequency (254Hz). After a few cycles the ACSPH scheme results in a lower frequency oscillation of the plate (~ 10 Hz), a result of the combined inertia and damping of the fluid-structure system. However, δ -SPH responds with a repeated and intermittent set of high-frequency oscillations. This is a common response observed with a WCSPH approach [26] where the time between oscillations is set by the time for acoustic waves generated at release to travel to the free-surface and back ($2H/c_0 = 80$ ms). These acoustic waves are clearly observed within figure 1 whereas ACSPH retains a hydrostatic gradient.

Following a series of oscillations the ACSPH scheme returns to a near steady state behaviour (~ 2 s) whereas the weakly compressible solution has a continually oscillating plate with a frequency of 6.2Hz $\sim 0.5c_0/2H$. The displacement decay is better observed considering the envelope of the displacement signal, as shown within figure 2(b). After the initial release stage, ACSPH shows a strong viscous damping behaviour arising from the fluid from 0.05-2.4 s. From 2.4 s onward the plate dynamics have the same damping ratio as the structure and no additional fluid influence. In contrast to this, the weakly compressible approach has a reduced damping in the initial damping regime and a larger than structural damping ratio (~ 8 times) in the quasi-steady response following 1.5s. The aforementioned damping response of the structure is also clearly replicated in the kinetic energy decay of the fluid, as

Fig. 2: Results for the hydrostatic watercolumn supported by an elastic plate.

shown in figure 2(c), where ACSPH resolves the kinetic energy to the point where there are no significant oscillations.

This behaviour in both the initial and final stages of the δ -SPH response can only be attributed to the presence of false acoustic waves and weak-compressibility. This could be resolved by increasing the artificial speed of sound to better match the ratio of wave-speeds between the fluid and structure, but this would result in a more expensive simulation ($\Delta t \propto 1/c_0$).

B. Dam-break

To evaluate the artificial-compressibility method in the case of fluid-structure impacting, the standard SPH dambreak is now explored. The geometry of this case follows directly from Lobovský *et al.* [27] considering the initial fluid depth (H) of 300 mm only considering the lower pressure probe at $(x,y)=(1.61, 0.003)$ m here. A resolution of $H/\Delta x = 400$ is used with an artificial speed of sound of $c_0 = 50\sqrt{gH}$ in the δ -SPH model.

Visualisation of the resulting flow regime for both the AC and δ -SPH formulations are shown in figure 4, respectively. The initial pressure field is set to a hydrostatic solution rather than solving the relevant Poisson problem. ACSPH resolves the Laplacian pressure field immediately on the first step within the pseudo-iterations, whereas the weakly compressible approach results in repeated pressure fluctuations as the free surface pressure condition is resolved in physical time. Following the fluid-boundary impact and over-topping of the wave in

the second image at $t\sqrt{gH} = 6.06$, significant acoustic waves emerge in the WCSPH solution and propagate throughout the flow. ACSPH resolves the incompressible field well here, shown in the pressure measurements in figure 3(a). The experimental results of Lobovský *et al.* [27] are included for completeness, there are differences against the experimental profiles but this is to be expected, most importantly the AC and WCSPH pressures show consistent profiles.

Subsequently, time instants during the fluid-fluid impact and closure of internal voids are shown in the lower two rows of figure 4. The acoustic noise in the WCSPH solution is dominant here and completely obscures the incompressible solution, which is well recovered in ACSPH. To observe this influence, the complete time history from the pressure probe is shown in figure 3(b), highlighting the acoustic waves as large-amplitude high-frequency oscillations. Note, these pressure oscillations are fairly consistent with unfiltered WCSPH results, for instance Sun *et al.* [28] (without the acoustic damper), where the magnitudes differ here considering the higher speed of sound employed.

Figure 3(b) shows some high-amplitude oscillations in pressure within the ACSPH scheme, notably at $t\sqrt{gH} \sim 8.0$ and 8.2, as highlighted in the inset figure. These features occur when voids in the fluid are closed and the momentum difference has to be resolved to ensure an incompressible field. This results in a fairly stiff problem and can cause difficulty in the ACSPH scheme converging. However, the incompressible solution is converged in a few real-time steps resulting in pressure fluctuations which are resolved almost instantly. It is also beneficial to note the JST has improved pressure response at these instants, a result of locally switching to the Laplacian diffusion term to resolve local pressure gradients, likely resulting in a softer system to converge. This highlights the JST schemes improved ability to resolve impacting behaviour in the interior fluid.

C. Vertical sloshing

The final test case considered is a challenging problem for SPH, defined by repeated and violent fluid impacts from vertical excitation of a filled tank with coupled FSI response. This case follows directly from Constantin *et al.* [29] and involves a rectangular tank connected to a structure (the T-beam) which isolates purely the vertical degree of freedom. The structural model described in Constantin *et al.* [29] is used to capture structural dynamics with a strong coupling methodology, SPH is cast in the non-inertial reference frame such that the computed structural accelerations are imposed on the momentum equation (within \mathbf{f}_i in (26)) rather than moving boundaries. Only one case is considered here with 50% filling level and the maximum structural deflection (d_0) of 14 mm, resulting in vertical excitation with initial acceleration of 6g and 10.05 Hz frequency ($\omega/2\pi$). Particle resolution is set such that $0.5H/\Delta x = 100$ and a conservative speed of sound of $28\omega d_0$ is used. The surface tension model of Vergnaud *et al.* [20] is activated with $\sigma = 0.0728$ N/m.

Fig. 3: Pressure probe measurements during the dam-break simulations, 5% and 95% pressure percentiles from Lobovský *et al.* [27] are shown.

Fig. 4: Visualisation of the non-dimensional pressure field during the dam-break simulation at times $t(g/H)^{0.5} = \{0.29, 6.06, 8.29, 10.18\}$.

Figure 6 shows the violent impacting of the fluid against the tank walls at two separate time instances, highlighting the continued slamming behaviour. It is clear within the pressure field that the weakly-compressible solution contains acoustic waves interacting within the complex fluid topology, whereas ACSPH can resolve a much cleaner pressure distribution aside from some localised perturbations (arising from closure of voids). Integration of this pressure distribution along the tank walls provides the scalar (vertical) hydrodynamic force, visualised in figure 5(b). Here, the improvements in force prediction are clearly observed. Acoustic noise from the impulsive initial excitation is immediate in WSPH, but this manages to mostly decay within t/T_1 , the regime where the sloshing flow is

developing. Following this the impacting regime is developed and the resulting acoustic noise within the force is continuous, with an amplitude on the same magnitude as the mean force. Note, the force profile in the initial regime is continuous and finite, highlighting that the fluid remains connected to the lower tank surface and nonphysical bulk separation of the fluid from the boundary (a result of the tensile instability) is avoided. ACSPH fares better here and mostly recovers a clean hydrodynamic force, which matches the mean profile of the weakly compressible solution. It is not without noise and non-physical force spikes however, again mostly arising from incomplete convergence of the pseudo time iterations due to particle disorder during strong localised impacting. There is no noticeable difference between the AC-2L and AC-JST schemes here, largely due to the fragmented flow activating the free-surface Laplacian term. Further work is required to highlight deficiencies and improve the JST scheme in scenarios like this.

Nominally, this force signal could be filtered to remove the acoustic noise and recover the incompressible solution. This is exemplified in figure 5(b) where a 30 Hz lowpass filter is applied to the δ -SPH result, noticeably matching ACSPH. However, filtering within the FSI setting is not possible and the structural acceleration response is a direct result of the integrated pressures. A structure with significant inertia will generally act as a low-pass filter to remove high-frequency force components entering into the structures dynamics, however, here the artificially low speed of sound used in the weakly compressible solver results in noise remaining in the acceleration, as demonstrated in figure 5(a).

Fig. 5: Results of the T-beam simulations, showing the first 10 cycles following release.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The inclusion of artificial compressibility into SPH is presented and analysed on a series of benchmark cases. Theoretically,

Fig. 6: Snapshots following free-release of the T-beam at $t/T1 = \{2.0, 5.8\}$. Contour shows the non-dimensional pressure.

cal links are drawn between δ -SPH, pressure projection methods within ISPH and artificial compressibility. The presented scheme can be easily incorporated into a δ -SPH framework and is capable of eliminating acoustic noise and recovering an incompressible solution. A series of benchmarks, where benefits in pressure-field smoothness and an improved quality of FSI results are noted. The final test case considers repeated and violent fluid-structure impact, here the acoustic noise which hampers the weakly compressible hydrodynamic force measurements is almost entirely removed, resulting in improved prediction of the coupled structural dynamics.

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